

Supplementary materials for “Auditory discrimination of natural soundscapes”

Frédéric Apoux¹, Nicole Miller-Viacava¹, Régis Ferrière², Huanping Dai³, Bernie Krause⁴, Jérôme Sueur⁵ and Christian Lorenzi¹

¹ *Laboratoire des Systèmes Perceptifs, UMR CNRS 8248, Département d’Etudes Cognitives, Ecole normale supérieure, Université Paris Sciences et Lettres (PSL), Paris, 75005, France.*

² *International Research Laboratory for Interdisciplinary Global Environmental Studies (iGLOBES), CNRS, ENS-PSL University, University of Arizona, Tucson, AZ, 85721, USA.*

³ *Speech Language and Hearing Sciences, University of Arizona, Tucson, AZ 85721-0071, USA.*

⁴ *Wild Sanctuary, 1102 Princeton Drive, Sonoma, California, 95476, USA.*

⁵ *Museum National d’Histoire Naturelle, Département Systématique et Evolution, UMR 5202 CNRS, USM 601 MNHN, CP 50, Paris, France.*

I. LIFETIME EXPOSURE TO NATURAL SOUNDS QUESTIONNAIRE

Lifetime exposure to natural sounds questionnaire

ID Number (to be filled by the experimenter): _____

We are interested in knowing your exposure to natural sounds over your entire lifetime.

These sounds correspond to sounds of both living and non-living things.

For example, birds, insects, toads, frogs, mammals, rivers, lakes, sea shores, etc...

This questionnaire is divided into 4 parts:

- 1. Mobility:** to assess your daily exposure due to the places where you have lived, even for short periods.
- 2. Holidays:** to assess your exposure to natural sounds due to going to rural environments for holidays.
Some examples are presented at the end of this page.
- 3. Occupational:** to assess your regular exposure to natural sounds due to your occupation.
- 4. Non-Occupational:** to assess your regular exposure to natural sounds due to any recreational and leisure activities, excluding holidays, that you have participated frequently in over your lifetime.

Scale to evaluate how wild the places are:

- 1- Large and dense permanent human settlement.
The landscape is mainly composed of infrastructure and build environment.
- 2- Small permanent human settlement, but with higher density population.
Human altered public areas and infrastructure becomes noticeable.
- 3- Small permanent clustered human settlement or community, but with low density population.
Dwellings are closer to one another, not scattered broadly. Nature still predominates in the landscape.
- 4- Area with very low density of human population.
Dwellings are mostly isolated or separated from neighbours by big portions of land.
- 5- Area where the land is in its natural state; where impacts from human activities are minimal.

Scale to evaluate your time exposure:

Yearly- an average close to 3 days per year.

Monthly- an average close to 3 days per month.

Weekly- an average close to 3 days per week.

Daily- at least once per day.

Holidays filling examples:

How wild was the environment?			How often have you been there?				How long did you stay there?
3	4	5	Once	Yearly	Monthly	Weekly	Write the total number of days

“ I went camping to a quiet national park for 2 weekends every year from ages 13 to 17 ” (2d x 2w x 5y = 20)

National park name and country	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	20
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“ I went to visit my parents in the countryside for 3 months each year from ages 15 to 23” (30d x 3m x 9y = 810)

Village name and country	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	810
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“ I went to a small and isolated town 3 days per week every year from ages 18 to 20” (3d x 4w x 12m x 3y = 432)

Town name and country	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	432
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“ I went once to a virgin forest for 8 weeks “ (7d x 8w = 56)

Forest name and country	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	56
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II. QUESTIONNAIRE METRIC

Here are the details of how the metric of the questionnaire was computed.

For each section a exposure score was computed as follows

$$\text{Mobility: } \sum^{\text{cities}} \text{Years} \times \text{Wildness weight}$$

$$\text{Holidays: } \sum^{\text{places}} \frac{\text{days stayed}}{360} \times \text{Wildness weight}$$

$$\text{Occupational: } \sum^{\text{jobs}} \text{Years} \times \frac{\text{exposure frequency}}{360} \times \text{Wildness weight}$$

$$\text{Non-Occupational: } \sum^{\text{activities}} \text{Years} \times \frac{\text{exposure frequency}}{360} \times \text{Wildness weight}$$

where the exposure frequency was computed using the same scale reported by Griest-Hines et al. 2021 as

Scale Selected	Time Assigned
Daily	5 (d/w) x 52 (w) = 260 days
Weekly	3 (d/w) x 52 (w) = 152 days
Monthly	3 (d/m) x 12 (m) = 36 days
Yearly	3 (d/y) x 01 (y) = 3 days

and the wildness weight was defined and assigned as

Scale Selected	Weight Assigned
5	1
4	0.75
3	0.5
2	0.25
1	0

After this, the **final exposure score metric** for a given participant was computed as the average of the four sections

$$\frac{1}{4} (\text{Mobility} + \text{Holidays} + \text{Occupational} + \text{Non-Occupational}) .$$

so each section of the questionnaire impacts the metric in the same way.